

Research Article

THE USE OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH IN THE AGE OF COVID-19			Education
		Keywords: New technology, learning English, classroom, teachers, advantages and disadvantages.	
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Abstract			
<p>Whether to use or not new technology inside the classroom has always been discussed for various reasons. Nowadays, technology is becoming an integral part of everybody's life (Hongling & Zhang, 2012). Considering the benefits that the use of new technologies could provide to people, especially those for learning English, research on this topic has been deemed worthwhile. Having in mind the counter-arguments, the present paper aims to investigate the advantage of using new technology in a class, and most importantly, how to use it and promote learning, advantages and disadvantages of using new technology in the classroom, how to encourage students to use IT appropriately, and exploring some of the best ways to teach and learn English language (Hermans et al. 2008).</p>			

I. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this research will be to find out whether the use of new technologies helps in learning English (Spahiu & Spahiu, 2016). It is well known that our nowadays life is highly affected by the use of new technology devices, and technology plays an essential role in today's human society development (Spahiu & Spahiu, 2010). Based on this fact, it is indispensable to benefit from new technological devices in English language learning. Many factors affect the success and achievement of students. The elements are of different natures; some are related to professors' responsibilities, while others are related to students' responsibilities. Thus, nowadays, much attention has been focused on using education technology in classes, which helps teachers realize better and more effective learning (Shyamlee & Solanki, 2012).

Technology is an excellent tool, but not everyone uses technology for good purposes; others use it only for waste of time (Spahiu & Spahiu, 2016). New technologies offer opportunities for taking account of individual proficiency and interest. Recent studies in this area indicate that effective use of education technology can help the education system work better and effectively. So, suppose you know how to manage your time and take advantage of everything in life. In that case, the technology can also provide many learning opportunities, especially for those interested in learning English. Music is everywhere; it is on the radio, on television, on our smart phones,

and even in the cafeterias and restaurants where we go to relax. When you listen to a record in English, you need to pay attention to the **lyrics because** you might learn some new English expressions. After all, when listening to a song, you can notice if the words are pronounced correctly, and it is a pretty good method to keep things in mind and simultaneously enrich the vocabulary.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEMS

The purpose of this study will be to find out the impact of using new technology devices in learning English and explore if the students find it out helpful and attractive. The reason why we this topic is chosen is that nowadays more innovative programs and web pages are coming out. These programs provide excellent opportunities to learn pure English, being offered at a very affordable price for the population, even without the teachers' help if you do not have economic opportunities pursuing special English language courses. The olden days of limited options for education are already gone and all thanks to technological advances.¹

Technology provides numerous opportunities to learn various things that we are curious to know, compared with the past when we have not remembered in this kind of way.

The primary objectives of this study will be:

1. To explore the influence of new technology devices in learning English.
2. To identify which technological devices are mainly used.
3. To investigate the benefits that the use of new technologies could bring in learning English.

Technology plays an essential role for students because it affects the success and development of students directly. Was this research worth doing on using new technologies in learning English? The study will be focused basically on three main research questions, which are:

1. Do the teachers use new technologies in the English classes?
2. Which technological devices are mainly used?
3. What benefits could bring the use of new technologies in learning English?

This study dares to hypothesize: the use of new technologies in learning English. Research questions correspond with specific structural aspects of the topic, such as:

- Do the teachers use new technologies in the classroom?
- Is it hard to learn how to use new technologies?
- Which technological devices we use in the classroom?
- Do technology devices motivate students to learn the English language in more attractive manners?

¹<https://www.tefl-online.com/tefl-jobs/online-tefl-articles/technology-learning-english/>

- Is the use of TV, music, films, computers are influencing learning English?

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section includes specific details about the method for collecting data for the survey. The study is conducted using a quantitative approach entirely online. The survey is used to perform the study, including data collection and interpretation, primarily through questionnaires. The questionnaires are distributed to fifty students in North Macedonia from various cultural backgrounds. This English course was selected because it has the most students and is, therefore, more advanced in modern technology. In the final stage of this research, we collected data from students' interviews, questionnaires, and statistics. Besides this presentation, from the data collected, we give conclusions, suggestions to the students' academic performances

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

It is important to note the gender aspect of the respondents from the student's side who took the survey, where as it can be seen from the graphical presentation, the vast majority were male, whereas a slight percentage preferred not to disclose their gender.

The effort given by the teachers is crucial in the learning process and there are no more suitable respondents to give an overview for such an issue as the students themselves. As can be seen from the graph the majority of the students believe teachers have done a good job in organizing and providing the needed efforts to make the learning process as successful as possible. Although there were students who thought that the efforts were poor, nevertheless, things look good, at least for the given aspect.

When asked about the skills used during the learning process during the pandemic, the data show that Listening skills are the ones upon which students mostly agree, followed by Speaking, Reading and Writing. We believe that this comes as no surprise considering the fact that online teaching is usually based on sound and speaking, especially if we mention that both teachers and students need to use microphones and headphones during the learning process.

Data acquired for the question concerning course organization is interesting for the fact that, as in the previous question, a considerable number of students had a neutral approach to this aspect. This issue changes drastically when responding about student participation during the lessons. Overall, the majority of students have a positive attitude towards course organization, however, further research should be done in order to assess why many of them are neutral in many aspects.

What aspects of online courses were most useful or valuable?

32 responses

The visual learning part was the most enjoyable part especially presentations or videos; Listening skills improved; Presentations, seminars and essays were a majestic step for academic education. Moreover, we have been preparing for digital meetings so that we will successfully appear into future online conferences. Some of professors evaluated us via presentations that were a great idea they understood deeply our intelligence and accuracy of language knowledge; Listening and speaking; Reading, writing, listening and speaking; Instructions about the lesson; Participation of the students and the extra explanation the students needed for their seminar papers; We could listen to the courses from home so we had more time to learn; Speaking aspects; We were able to listen to the lectures from our homes, without the need to travel to university; Learning in a different perspective; Maybe speaking skills; Listening the lesson, comprehend the subject better; Students had the comfort to study from their homes; thus, it was much easier for students from further regions who had to travel previously; all in general; Most; exams; Learning; Online courses are convenient, online courses offer flexibility, online courses offer more individual attention, online courses give you real world skills etc; We can learn at our own pace; All; Answer and question; Nothing at all; Engagement, participation, listening, writing, feedback; Using technology to send homework in real-time.

How would your teachers improve their online courses?

35 responses

Perhaps by giving everyone the same opportunities to express themselves freely without interruption; By adding more presentations; Patience and clarity should be closely tied when it comes to discussion; professors should ask twice students what is wrong with them, in order to avoid conflicts. On the other hand, they have to

check out if the technological devices are working properly, avoiding the voice repetition. You can never know what is happening in other corner of world therefore professors and students should transparently corporate for bring a notorious generation even though the pandemic is a little bit blocking us; By explaining clearly the course; Maybe by them opening the camera, I think it would be better; In their best way; Sharing PowerPoint presentations; Maybe try to think outside the box sometimes and take examples of different objects in our everyday life routine so that everyone can have a clear idea of what's the topic about; Communicating more with students and not stressing them out during conversations; When lets students more to speak; By adapting to the online teaching, by using Google Meet and Classroom; Allow students to decide whether they want to answer questions or not and to give them much more time for homework and presentations or seminar paper; Maybe by turning on their cameras, and letting student participate equally during the classes. And by reducing the time length of the class, a short one but more effective. But overall the system was organized badly, and there was lack of seriousness by both, teachers and students; By giving the student more space and being more understandable; Learn more IT :) also learns at least a programming language. This age belongs to technology!; Interacting with students a little bit more and giving out homework more often; Its ok; I think by opening their cameras and talking to us more, engaging us into conversation to better our English, etc; participating more; With writing; When teachers are in an online setting where they have to teach, there can be pressure to be "on" all the time. They may feel pressure to be constantly available for students since they aren't face-to-face to teach them during the day; Helping students maintain focus and motivation; Good; I think its okay; By asking more questions; Engaging different activities that will keep students interested in participating, motivate them, while lecturing ask questions and when receiving an answer then give feedback; Using more tech tools.

The aforementioned responses are self-explanatory where student involvement and technology are some of the most important issues that pertain to the learning process in an online environment. It comes as no surprise that technology is at the forefront during this kind of learning, therefore, grasping and using such technology at its best will certainly affect such processes in the future.

The question of cameras has always been a very hot topic during online lessons, where most of the time students complain that although they are required to have their cameras on, most of the teachers’ prefer not to show themselves on online classrooms. Our survey is no different in this regard. More 68% of the students said that their teacher never or rarely turn their cameras on. In many ways this is very important for the fact that teachers are those who need to organize a lesson, therefore their “lack of presence” can profoundly affect the learning process as a whole, which may result in student ignorance and neutral behavior as seen from their responses in some of the previous questions.

In compliance with the previous answers, we see that student involvement is not an issue that represents any major problems in the learning environment. Data shows that most of the students believe that teacher provide enough opportunities for them to be involved and engaged during classes, which is very positive given the fact that we always strive to making learning more interactive where students are the main focus of learning.

The gender of the following respondents is almost the same for female and male, meaning that the data should represent a somewhat balanced view of how male and female teachers view the issue of online teaching and learning process.

We believe that it was expected that the vast majority of respondents will fall between the age of 30 to 49. This is important for the fact that we are dealing with somewhat young respondents which means that they were able to grasp and master the new technologies appropriately, therefore, making their responses more significant.

Data acquired for the question of teacher expectation is quite interesting if we consider that the majority responded that they are neutral in their expectations of whether students can provide the same input as in physical presence. This may be as a result that most of them have dealt with this kind of learning for the first time and they are still not able to profoundly assess issue like these, but what makes things even more difficult is the fact that only 23.5% have responded that they agree that expectations should be the same. We believe that if teachers were more prepared for this kind of teaching environment and if in the future these methods and techniques can be further used, things may change more rapidly.

Data shows that although teachers faced some difficulties, nevertheless, it seems that they have usually found a way to master the technology and adapt properly to such environment.

It is obvious from the graph that the vast majority of the teacher believe that student motivation is profoundly affected by online learning and they are of the opinion that motivation is way higher in face-to-face learning compared to online. We believe that this is also a result of the

fact that our schools have been facing this kind of learning for the first time and operational and technological issue have had a huge impact on the learning process.

Live streaming of lectures is somewhere according to the responses acquired; this is mainly due to the fact that it doesn't have a crucial importance for the quality of the teaching and learning process.

This graph represents a somewhat different view on motivation, because we see that most have responded that they meet the standards. This difference compared to the previous question is probably because it has been asked in parallel with engagement, which as we saw was at a good level.

Learner, Instructor and Content challenges are on the same level according to data acquired through our questionnaire, meaning that all these aspects are crucial and require equal approach for a successful teaching and learning process.

Responses for the participation during online teaching are in accordance with those acquired from the students, meaning that participation and engagement are at a good degree.

This question is very important for its specific nature. But what is surprising is that most of the teachers have responded that they are able to support students who have emotional and behavioral disorders. This is crucial for the fact that these issues usually require direct contact with such students, and if this is actually true, this is a very positive aspect in an online learning environment.

There is a somewhat negative mood regarding whether students can be well prepared for the real world through online learning. The vast majority either is undecided or disagrees that students can be ready to face the real world. We believe that there should be further research regarding this issue to see why teachers have such opinion, especially considering the fact that in our schools, even in face-to-face teaching we don't actually have many practical lessons which can prepare students for real-world tasks.

Regarding the issue of negative effect on grading, teachers are divided on whether they agree or disagree, and what is most important is that a huge percentage of 47.1 are undecided. We believe that this has to do with the fact that we mentioned before regarding the novelty of the technology and methods.

Although the majority of teachers are of the opinion that the exam.net platform is accurate for grading, still, many, 35.3% are undecided. We believe that this has to do, at least to a certain degree, with the proper grasp of the technology; nevertheless, we see that the platform has been used with good results.

The responses for this question are more or less in the same pattern as with any other regarding technological grasp of the various online learning platforms. In this case, we see that most of the respondents are not sure of the degree of challenge Google Meet represents for the students and instructors. This can be seen as a direct result of the novelty of the platform for most of them, and the lack of proper, previous, acquaintance with such technologies.

The graph shows that ethics does not represent a problem for online learning for the majority of respondents, although 23.5% think that there is a lack of ethics. Moreover, it important to emphasize the 23.5 % of those who are undecided, which goes in accordance with the data acquired with the previous questions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This section provides information that we gathered about the findings of this research. These findings mainly focused on this research's central hypothesis, such as how new technologies help learn English. Do the teachers use technology in the classroom to learn the English language? The benefits of using technology in learning English and which teachers mostly use technology devices to make their lectures interactive to learn English more easily. The expected results show how technological devices such as computers, innovative tables, projectors, radios, televisions and so on have a considerable influence in learning English during the age of COVID 19 and teacher used all these devices during this time (Capan, 2012). Listening to any song or watching any film during English classes helps a lot in students' engagement and motivation and makes the lesson more attractive; therefore, things come more naturally. Compared to traditional classroom teaching and learning, this study's findings show that technology-based teaching and learning are more successful. Using ICT resources and equipment would provide a more engaging and productive learning experience for both teachers and students. To summarize, the first stage of ICT implementation (Cassim & Obono, 2011) must be adequate for teachers and students to make the most of it. As a result, technology-based teaching and learning plans begin with the school's top management's proper implementation and support. ICT integration in schools would be a massive success and benefit for both teachers and students if the implementation phase of technology integration in schools is done correctly from the start and ongoing maintenance is adequately supported (Spahiu & Spahiu, 2016). Teachers must have enough time to study and explore ICT and go through the “trial-and-error” process until they are entirely comfortable with it and can use it for teaching and learning. Finally, to improve the country's educational system's competency, introducing ICT in the classroom needs serious consideration. All this will strengthen the national education's global ranking and create a more robust future workforce. To promote ICT use in the school, the government must improve and shift teachers' attitudes toward ICT integration. Teachers play a critical role to ensure that every new strategy is implemented effectively. Advanced technology and communication devices should be accessible to students

wherever they are, whether at school or home, to drive the occurring improvements. Furthermore, teachers must be literate and have good skills and experience in using ICT to encourage productive learning and meet the demand for 21st-century teaching skills; teachers should use ICT to develop their teaching methods and approach (Hongling & Zhang, 2012; Cassim & Obono, 2011). Issues and challenges of ICT integration may be overly familiar, but in-depth studies of ICT integration in schools' core subjects are seldom addressed. It would be beneficial if further research could be done into the challenges that teachers face when using ICT in their everyday classrooms in schools (Hongling & Zhang, 2012; Cassim & Obono, 2011). Furthermore, rather than concentrating only on public schools, it is preferable to conduct this research in private schools in North Macedonia. We have three prominent colleges: public schools, Albanian schools, and Macedonian schools. Some schools will have more money, making ICT implementation (Cassim & Obono, 2011) much quicker and simpler. It is beneficial if comparisons can be made between different schools so that the positive aspects can be used as examples and changes can be made to the shortcomings found. Besides that, comparative studies of ICT integration in teaching and learning between public and private schools are strongly recommended. It's because most private schools allow students to bring devices to class, and the teaching and learning process is conducted using ICT. The effects of the success of ICT incorporation in pubs will be interesting to see.

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